

Synthesis of Flavan-oximinotosylates and their Antimicrobial Activity

VIDYA JOSHI* and P. N. PATIL

Institute of Science, 15 Madam Cama Road, Bombay-400 032

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IN our work on Neber rearrangement we have synthesised a few new flavan-oximinotosylates as intermediates and evaluated their biological activity.

Results and Discussion

In the present paper we have described the synthesis of a few flavan-oximinotosylates (3a-g). On testing their antifungal and antibacterial activity they were found to be inactive.

2'-Hydroxy-4'-methoxychalcones¹ (1a-g) by cyclisation gave flavanones² (2a-g) by the usual method (Scheme 1). The flavanones (2a-g) on reacting with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate in ethanol yielded the oximes which were tosylated to yield the tosyl derivatives (3a-g; Table 1) out of which only 3a, b are reported in literature³. It was observed that yield of the tosyl derivatives obtained by (i) *p*-CH₃C₆H₄SO₂Cl-K₂CO₃-acetone method (57-74%) was much higher than that obtained by (ii) *p*-CH₃C₆H₄SO₂Cl-anhydrous pyridine method (40-60%).

- 1-3a; R=H; R₁=H; R₂=H
 b; R=H; R₁=OCH₃; R₂=H
 c; R=H; R₁=CH₃; R₂=H
 d; R=OCH₃; R₁=OCH₃; R₂=H
 e; R=H; R₁=Cl; R₂=H
 f; R=H; R₁R₂=-O-CH₂-O-
 g; R=OCH₃; R₁=OCH₃; R₂=OCH₃

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) H₂SO₄ (4%), EtOH, 40-80 h, (ii) NH₂OH.HCl, CH₃COONa, EtOH, (iii) *p*-CH₃-C₆H₄SO₂Cl, anhydrous K₂CO₃, (CH₃)₂C=O.

Biological activity: Earlier workers reported bacteriostatic and antifungal activities⁴ of 2-hydroxychalcones and hence we had decided to test the activities of the synthesised compounds. Antifungal activity was tested against *T. mentagrophyte*, *T. rubrum* and *C. albicans* and antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *S. typhi*. All the compounds 1a-g and 3a-g were found to be inactive at 200 μg ml⁻¹ concentration.

Elemental analyses are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	132	71	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ NO ₅ S
3b	131	71	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ NO ₆ S
3c	129	71	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ NO ₅ S
3d	150	74	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ NO ₅ S
3e	148	63	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ ClNO ₅ S
3f	145	68	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ NO ₇ S
3g	176	57	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ NO ₆ S

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Experimental

General procedure. 4-Chloro-7-methoxy-4-N-(*p*-toluenesulphonyloximino)flavan (3e): A mixture of 4'-chloro-7-methoxy-4-oximinoflavan (800 mg) obtained from flavanone 2e, *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (900 mg), anhydrous potassium carbonate

(12 g) and dry acetone (90 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 24 h. Anhydrous potassium carbonate was removed by filtration and the filtrate evaporated. The resulting gummy residue was washed with water and crystallised from acetone-methanol, yield (750 mg, 62.5%), m.p. 148°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 630 (C=N), 1 380, 1 190 (SO₂), 1 275 (C-O-C) and 965 cm⁻¹ (N-O).

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